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Teamwork skills development in hybrid and online universities: the perspective of the future teachers

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Abstract

The development of the teamwork competence is a demand for university education that is particularly difficult to meet in distance education (online and blended learning), where it is still relatively little researched. The teacher plays a fundamental role in introducing this type of activities in the class and motivating students who often do not like this kind of tasks. If the teachers/instructors are not convinced of the interest of teamwork, it will be difficult for them to achieve a successful introduction. Using a survey designed ad hoc for this investigation to collect the data, this article details the results on the perceptions of teamwork by 298 students in the degree of Education, future teachers, from one of the largest blended learning universities in Europe. It is observed that those students who opt for teamwork are more involved with their own learning and the development of new skills. Among them, those who think that teamwork allows them to develop interpersonal skills are more likely to opt for it. Employability also appears as an important factor for the students who prefer teamwork. On the negative side, practical aspects for the student usually appear related to teammate trust and distance in these kinds of learning environments. Our results allowed a better understanding of the future teachers' perceptions of teamwork and, consequently, new strategies can be designed to boost the use to collaborative learning in their prospective careers.

Keywords: Teamwork, Blended learning, Collaborative learning, Online teaching, Group work

1 Introduction

The development of generic skills is a growing demand from the students to their universities, and also from the employers (Volkov & Volkov, 2015; Bridgstock, 2009; Clarke, 2018). Higher education has to ensure that the required future, soft, and employability skills are transferred to students who become the workforce (Li & Ironsi, 2024; Teng et al., 2019). Universities are showing an increased interest in equipping their students with these types of capabilities (Nisha, & Rajasekaran, 2018; Navío-Marco et al., 2023). As OECD points out (Ananiadou et al., 2009), developments in society and economy require that educational systems provide citizens with the so called twenty-first century

skills and competencies,¹ which allow them to benefit from the emerging new forms of socialisation in a system where the main asset is knowledge.

According to the literature, teamworking is an essential skill expected of our graduates to perform their work and enhance employability, together with the ability to resolve problems, communicate and use technology to integrate this in the teaching process, among others (Fajaryati & Akhyar, 2020; Sokhanvar et al., 2021, for systematic literature reviews). Moreover, teamwork and peers' collaboration can increase the academic performance of the student in distance education (Oyelere, et al., 2021).

Online and blended learning universities should also promote the acquisition of these skills, but their acquisition may be hindered in technology-mediated distance learning virtual environments, where one of the major challenges is to maintain the benefits of interaction and learning among students (Solórzano-García & Navío-Marco, 2019). But at the same time, the advent of the COVID-19 pandemic has led to a rapid expansion of this type of teaching and has generated greater interest in investigating how to teach and learn in non-face-to-face environments (Tonbuloglu & Tonbuloglu, 2023; Zhou et al., 2022; Okoye et al., 2021) also exploring the different strategies that work in face-to-face and whose benefits should also be achieved in non-face-to-face environments (Dumford & Miller, 2018; Halverson & Graham, 2019; Muir et al., 2019; Navío-Marco et al., 2022).

Particularly for the acquisition and practice of teamwork, there is a flourishing research for online learning, showing advantages of teamwork in the acquisition of other competences (Volkov & Volkov, 2015), challenges to be addressed (Chang & Kang, 2016; Donelan & Kear, 2023), and especially about differences with the much more studied teamwork in in-person learning environments (Konak et al., 2019; Saghafian & O'Neill, 2018). It also begins to reflect on the role of the instructor to promote its practice and use as part of such studies (Pei et al., 2023). Teamwork in hybrid learning presents specific challenges compared to other contexts, especially to define and work with the appropriate combination of environments (face-to-face and online): The hybrid work model requires additional planning to ensure that the little face-to-face time the team has is optimally used for tasks that are best performed in person, in particular team building, strategic discussions, defining objectives and purpose (Buła, Thompson & Žak, 2024), Instructors need to spend more time designing how students should work in these combined environments (Gomez et al., 2009), providing complete and detailed instructions, as well as finding the best way to take advantage of synchronous and asynchronous environments. Additionally, some challenges from the online environments remain applicable, such as the difficulties for integration and the sense of isolation.

In this sense, the fundamental role of the instructor cannot be underestimated in order to involve students in teamwork activities, to help in the acquisition of this competence or to increase the motivation and performance of these students thanks to these activities. But to achieve this goal, the instructor himself must be convinced of the intrinsic value of this type of practice. As we shall see, previous research is limited when providing recommendations

¹ Twenty-first century skills have been proposed at the heart of individual learning by organizations such as the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization (UNESCO), the Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD), Partnership for 21st Century Skills (P21) or Assessment and Teaching of the 21st Century Skills ATC21S (González-Salamanca, Agudelo & Salinas, 2020). The use of ICT platforms is fundamental in each of the twenty-first century skills frameworks (Kadijevich, Gutvajin & Ljubojevic, 2023).

for teachers, but these recommendations are of little use if the first to be convinced of the value of these learning strategies are the teachers themselves.

That is why this research focuses on understanding if there are different perceptions and patterns of behavior among future teachers regarding teamwork. For this purpose, we analyze an experience of teamwork among 298 students of the degree of Education at one of the largest blended learning universities in Europe. Their attitude, vision and valuation of teamwork will allow us to better understand their approach to teamwork, and to define strategies for them to positively value its use in their future as teachers.

This research analyses a teamwork learning experience in the asynchronous (digital) part of blended teaching, encouraging our students of Education to work in teams. Students were given the option to either engage in group work or tackle tasks individually, with subsequent feedback solicited via survey upon task completion. The primary objective was to discern potential behavioral tendencies and perceptual disparities between students opting for group collaboration versus those favoring individual endeavors. To achieve this aim, six specific research questions guided the investigation. The first four questions aimed to explore the perceptions of the entire student sample regarding teamwork, irrespective of the assignment modality chosen.

These questions are as follows: 1) What are the students' perceptions of teamwork regarding its contribution to their education?, 2) What difficulties do students face when engaging in teamwork? 3) What factors influence students' decisions when choosing between teamwork and individual work?, 4) According to students' perceptions, what skills do they acquire through teamwork?. The final two research questions were focused specifically on students who chose to complete the assignment in teams: 5) From their experience in this course, to what extent do students believe that teamwork helps in building learning communities, and does this belief vary based on their intention to work in teams on future projects?, and 6) What factors influence students' decisions to choose teamwork again after having opted for this modality during their assignment during this term?

These specific research questions aim to unravel the motivations driving distance learners to opt for teamwork when presented with the choice, and also what students' perceptions of teamwork allow us to predict the type of work that students choose (individual/teams). Consequently, this research contributes to a deeper comprehension of teamwork learning mechanisms, particularly pertinent for future teachers who must recognize and advocate for the efficacy of such approaches in their pedagogical practices. Moreover, it serves as a call to propagate and endorse the adoption of teamwork learning methodologies.

The rest of the article is structured in the following manner: this introduction is followed by Sect. 2, which outlines the theoretical framework of the research, followed by the presentation of the methodology and the data used in Sect. 3, and then by the empirical analysis and discussion in Sect. 4. The article ends with the conclusions, which also include the limitations of the article and future lines of research.

2 Theoretical framework

2.1 Teamwork in blended and online environments

The dynamics of teamwork, as well as learning based on collaboration and interaction with the rest of the students, members of the team, have their roots in the constructivist theory of learning. The team is actually a Zone of Proximal Development,

according to Vygotsky (1962, 1978) in which the student also learns from the peers. It also connects with the social cognitive theory (Bandura, 1999, 2004, 2006) where learning occurs in a social context with a dynamic and mutual interaction with others and the environment. Ultimately, it is also linked with the concept of learning ecologies, as a set of contexts of activities, resources, relationships, and interactions that emerge from them (Barron, 2006; Sangrá et al., 2019).

In the field of online learning, teamwork and collaboration between students is already beginning to have a relevant reflection in the literature. Collaboration in online learning has been shown to promote learning, social interaction, communication, problem-solving skills, critical thinking, creativity, motivation, and personal satisfaction in the educative process through engagement in knowledge construction with peers (Oyelere et al., 2021; Tsai, 2013; Tseng & Yeh, 2013). Psychosocial factors, such as relationship building, cohesion, and trust, are crucial for the effectiveness of virtual teams (Magana et al., 2022).

Donelan & Kear (2023) when studying persistent challenges and implications for practice in online group projects in higher education, established that the key challenges were: low and uneven participation by students, a lack of clarity and preparation for students, and poor relationships. These poor relationships include difficulty in getting to know peers in the group (Saghafian & O'Neill, 2018) and managing irresponsible students (such as free riders or slackers) who become a burden, doing less than the rest (Scherling, 2011).

Tseng, Wang, Ku, and Sun (2009) include organisation practices as factor to explain online collaborative satisfaction. Ku, Tseng and Akarasriworn, (2013) in their study about collaboration factors, teamwork satisfaction, and student attitudes, considered as critical elements in a successful online collaborative setting: a) instructor support and encouragement, b) team commitment, c) clear objectives and goals, d) clear communication, e) timely resources, f) frequent communication, g) use of interactive software, h) synchronous meetings, i) opportunities to access and view examples, and j) well-defined and well-organized instruction. Additionally, Garcia and Privado (2023) point out that four extracted collaboration factors: communication, trust, cooperation and cohesion, show moderate to high degrees of correlation with cooperative work satisfaction. Other factors commonly mentioned in the literature are leadership, safety or autonomy provided to group members (Ortega et al. 2010; Mundell and Pennarola, 1999).

On the other hand, further communication, conflict resolution and negotiation skills are built through teamwork to encourage adaptability in students (Volkov & Volkov, 2015), while also enabling students to develop problem solving and critical thinking in online classes (Tseng & Yeh, 2013).

Along with the aforementioned aspects, and particularly the interpersonal and collaborative ones, such remote environments require student self-regulatory processes (Pool et al., 2017; Villatoro Moral & De Benito, 2021), promoting personal active involvement, responsibility and introducing a problem-based focus (Boelens et al., 2017). Right self-regulated learning strategies in online courses motivate students to strive for a good teamwork experience (Oyelere, et al., 2021). The self-regulation theory to study group processes and collaborative learning can be expanded, by including

sociocultural and situational concepts, towards a socially-shared regulation of learning: students working in teams collectively regulate their learning processes (Goñi, et al. 2020).

As far of our knowledge, there are no studies that specifically delve into the teamwork skill development in blended learning universities. This may be because teamwork activities are usually carried out in the asynchronous part of these learning environments, so the online component can condition its characteristics and hide potential specific aspects. Some authors such as Pei et al. (2023) analysing the sense of community in blended education, observe that interpersonal conflicts, issues with time management, role ambiguity, and cultural differences are obstacles to high-quality group work.

In any case, it would be interesting to try to take greater advantage of the benefits of hybrid environments so that the combination of online and face-to-face would be fruitful to offer a richer and more complete teamwork experience.

2.2 Teamwork: the instructor side

When it comes to successful collaborative learning environment, the three elements of the Community of Inquiry must be considered: teaching, cognitive and social presence (Garrison et al., 1999; Magana, et al., 2022), also in blended learning settings (Vaughan & Garrison, 2006). In these environments the presence of the educator is especially valuable. In fact, as we already indicated, instructor support and encouragement can be considered one of the most relevant critical elements when it comes to teamwork in online collaborative learning (Ku, Tseng & Akarasriworn, 2013). Additionally, as Saghafian et al. (2018) indicate, support from course instructors may help alleviate the free rider problem.

Through in-class instruction and facilitation, instructors can promote student mastery of the collaborative processes needed for successful teamwork (Kottmeyer, Cutler, & Pembridge, 2018), managing peer authority and team conflicts. Instructors should define the appropriate group size, which can be larger in face-to-face and smaller online and recommending an intermediate number in the hybrid case, assign warm-up activities for team building in the first face-to-face class and supplement with online interactive games and “light” activities (Gomez et al., 2009). Likewise, they should reinforce with activity materials in asynchronous environments. Additionally, instructors should introduce proper teamwork assessment instruments designed for a summative evaluation of the individual contribution of each team member to the project outcomes and the project process (Konak et al., 2019).

The instructor must not only be convinced but also well prepared to support the groups. Professional development on sense of community for teachers is needed (Pei et al., 2023), Instructors have to be attentive and sensitive to the dynamic boundaries that are established in the group (such as dispersion, subteam formation, boundary spanning, multiteaming, and moving on and off the team) as Maślikowska, and Gibbert, (2023) suggest. In a nutshell, as indicated by Konak et al. (2019), online instructors should be more proactive in engaging with project teams.

Instructors need also to persuade their remote students of the value of group work in terms of students' upcoming professional practice. It is likely to be increasingly important in the workplace (Smith et al., 2011). As these authors indicate, given the norm of

individual asynchronous work in these environments and the associated communication and logistical challenges, instructors teaching should probably provide explicit, succinct written recommendations for how to operate in an online learning group environment.

3 Methodology and data

The study was carried out in the context of the subject Applied Statistics in Education in the Faculty of Education at one of the biggest hybrid universities in Europe. An ex-post-facto research design was employed in this investigation. In this course, students were given the option to complete one of the assignments in two modalities: individually or in teams, to understand if there are different perceptions and patterns of behavior among future teachers regarding teamwork.

Convenience sampling, based on the accessibility of students, was utilized to gather data from 298 participants. Upon the conclusion of the academic term and the submission of assignments by all enrolled students, an online survey was distributed to the entire cohort. To ensure comprehensive representation, the survey was resent on a weekly basis until all students had responded. Table 1 presents a summary of the main characteristics of the student sample, including gender, age, work situation, obligations limiting study time, and modality choice for the assignment, as students were given the option to complete the course assignment individually or in teams of two or three individuals.

A survey designed ad hoc for this investigation was used to collect the data. The survey comprised three blocks. The first block contained five demographic questions

Table 1 Descriptive statistics of the sample

Variables	Descriptives
<i>Gender</i>	
Men	15.4%
Women	82.9%
Other/I prefer not to respond	1.7%
<i>Age range</i>	
Between 18 and 30	26.8%
Between 31 and 45	43.3%
Between 46 and 50	17.5%
Between 51 and 65	12.4%
<i>Work situation</i>	
Not working	21.5%
Working part time	20.8%
Working full time	57.7%
<i>Students' obligations that limit their study time</i>	
Work	35.3%
People under their charge	11.4%
Both obligations	44.6%
None obligations	8.7%
<i>Students' choice regarding the modality of the assignment</i>	
Individually	30.6%
In group	69.4%

about the students. The second block was completed by all the students regardless the modality they chose to work on their paper (individually or in teams) and sought to measure:

- (a) The perceived utility of teamwork (13 items). The solution of the AFE of the 13-item perceived utility scale ($KMO=0.936$, $c^2(78)=3926$, $p<0.001$) explained 64.96% of the item variance and demonstrated a reliability of 0.97, as measured by the McDonald's omega statistic.
- (b) The possible difficulties the students face when they work in a team (7 items). The seven items pertaining to anticipated difficulties for students in regard to teamwork were found to cluster together into a single factor, which explained 61.59% of the item variance and exhibited a McDonald's omega value of 0.91 ($KMO=0.861$, $c^2(21)=1615.12$, $p<0.001$).
- (c) The skills the students think they develop during teamwork (8 items). A one factor solution was found regarding the students' perceptions of their skill acquisition ($KMO=0.953$, $c^2(28)=2161.53$, $p<0.001$), explaining 80.53% of the item variance. McDonald's omega statistic rendered a very good reliability.

The third block was designed specifically for students who chose teamwork, and it inquired about:

- (a) The most demanding task the students found during teamwork (8 items). The set of 8 items regarding the level of effort required by teamwork grouped together in one factor after the EFA ($KMO=0.908$, $c^2(28)=1124.45$, $p<0.001$) with a reliability of 0.92. This factor explained 60.0% of the item variance.
- (b) The students' perceptions about how teamwork helps build learning communities (4 items). The EFA of the four items devoted to measure the students' perceptions about the contribution of teamwork to forming learning communities yielded a one-factor solution explaining 82.09% of the variance and the reliability was 0.95 ($KMO=0.801$, $c^2(6)=808.38$, $p<0.001$).

All the items of each section are available in the Appendix. All items, except those in which categories were indicated, were measured on a 5-point Likert scale ranging from 1 to 5. The values of asymmetry and kurtosis ranged, respectively between -0.66 and 0.02 , and -1.29 and -0.72 . These values are acceptable to prove normality in the item distributions (Byrne, 2010).

To ensure the validity of the different scales designed ad hoc for this investigation, exploratory factor analyses (EFA) were carried out. The unweighted least squares extraction method followed by a Promax rotation were used. Scales reliabilities were estimated using the McDonald's omega statistic. Next, a descriptive analysis of the measured variables was conducted.

To compare the means of the variables considering the entire sample, the within-subjects repeated measures ANOVA technique (RM-ANOVA) was used. RM-ANOVA is the generalization of paired Students' t test. This technique is useful when the mean values in more than two traits of the same subjects are compared. Mauchly's

test was carried out prior to these analyses to study the sphericity assumption which was not met in any of the instances. For this reason, the degrees of freedom were corrected using the Greenhouse–Geisser approach. The effect size in RM-ANOVA was estimated using η^2 , with reference values for interpretation: <0.01 very small, $0.01–0.05$ small, $0.06–0.13$ moderate, and >0.14 large (López-Martín & Ardura, 2023). Mean differences for comparing groups of independent subjects were carried out using the Student's *t*-test, with the effect size estimated using Cohen's *d* statistic. Reference values for the interpretation of the effect size in this case are: <0.20 very small, $0.20–0.49$ small, $0.50–0.79$ moderate, and >0.80 large (López-Martín & Ardura, 2023).

Students' decision making was investigated using Chi-squared Automatic Interaction Detector (CHAID). The CHAID segmentation technique is a statistical method used to identify and segment a population into distinct groups based on a set of predictor variables. It is a decision tree algorithm that analyses relationships between a target variable and several predictor variables to create segments with homogeneous characteristics. The algorithm constructs a decision tree by repeatedly splitting the data based on the predictor variable that provides the most significant separation between groups. Each branch of the tree corresponds to a segment, and the tree grows until no further significant splits can be made. In this study, the criterion variable was the students' prospective decision on the modality (individual/in teams) for the next assignment. Thus, CHAID allowed us to find the best predictors of the students' future intentions.

The data collection was conducted by means of an online survey following the completion of the course and after students had submitted their papers. Informed consent was obtained from all participants, and confidentiality and anonymity of participants were meticulously maintained throughout the data collection phase and subsequent analyses.

4 Empirical results

4.1 Students' perceptions of teamwork contributions to their education and what difficulties they anticipate

A RM-ANOVA was performed to compare the mean values of the students' perceptions of the contributions of teamwork to them (see Table 2). Significant mean differences were found, $F(6.61, 1931.58) = 18.28$, $p < 0.001$, $h^2 = 0.053$. Post hoc comparisons unveiled that, on average, students perceived the greatest benefits of teamwork to be associated with the enhancement of their communication skills (3.36), the facilitation of generating new knowledge (3.32), meeting educational needs (3.30), acquainting themselves with peers (3.27), mitigating isolation (3.24), and ultimately, fostering the creation of a learning community (3.23), without statistically significant mean differences among them. Nonetheless, these features, on average, significantly exceeded the perceived contributions of other factors presented to students (see Table 2).

When comparing students who worked individually with those who worked in a team, all potential contributions presented to the students in the survey demonstrated statistically significant differences, except for the enhancement of communication skills, acquaintance with classmates, establishment of a learning community, and mitigation of isolation (see Table 2). The remaining contributions exhibited statistically significant

Table 2 Students' perceptions regarding the contribution that teamwork can make for them

	Total		Team		Individual		Comparison		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	d
MOTIVATION	2.95	1.36	3.13	1.37	2.53	1.26	3.51	<.01	0.44
PERFORMANCE	3.03	1.40	3.24	1.41	2.56	1.31	3.97	<.01	0.51
RESPONSIBILITY	3.14	1.30	3.35	1.3	2.66	1.31	3.99	<.01	0.51
INVOLVEMENT	3.06	1.36	3.30	1.37	2.53	1.21	4.58	<.01	0.58
COLLABORATION	3.32	1.30	3.44	1.34	3.06	1.17	2.35	.02	0.30
COMMUNICATION	3.36	1.32	3.42	1.35	3.21	1.24	1.28	.20	0.16
EFFICIENCY	2.85	1.38	3.10	1.40	2.27	1.16	4.97	<.01	0.63
GRADES	2.99	1.37	3.17	1.37	2.60	1.30	3.32	<.01	0.42
WORKLOAD	2.91	1.42	3.08	1.42	2.52	1.33	3.15	<.01	0.40
CLASSMATES	3.27	1.35	3.31	1.34	3.18	1.36	0.77	.45	0.10
COMMUNITY	3.23	1.30	3.32	1.30	3.03	1.30	1.74	.08	0.22
ISOLATION	3.24	1.39	3.29	1.41	3.12	1.35	0.95	.34	0.12
EDUCATION	3.30	1.25	3.53	1.23	2.78	1.14	4.94	<.01	0.62
TOTAL	3.13	1.11	3.28	1.14	2.77	0.96	3.74	<.01	0.47

MOTIVATION: Increase your motivation for the subject; PERFORMANCE: Improve your performance in the subject; RESPONSIBILITY: Take responsibility for your own learning; INVOLVEMENT: Increase your involvement with the subject; COLLABORATION: Collaborate to build useful and meaningful knowledge; COMMUNICATION: Develop your communication and knowledge transmission skills; EFFICIENCY: Perform the task more efficiently; GRADES: Improve my grade in the subject; WORKLOAD: Decrease the workload; CLASSMATES: Get to know my classmates; COMMUNITY: Create a learning community; ISOLATION: Reduce the isolation of distance learning; EDUCATION: Necessary for my education

variances between these two student groups, with effect sizes ranging from small to moderate.

One of the largest effect sizes in mean differences was found in students' perceptions of the indispensability of teamwork for their educational pursuits ($d=0.62$). Furthermore, students who opted to work in a group believed that teamwork would enhance their efficiency ($d=0.63$), increase their engagement ($d=0.58$) and performance ($d=0.51$), and foster a sense of responsibility ($d=0.51$). Ultimately, they perceived that working in a team would bolster their motivation more than those who chose to work individually ($d=0.44$) (see Table 2).

In Table 3, the average results of anticipated difficulties are presented for the total sample and disaggregated based on whether the student chose to work in a team or not. A RM-ANOVA was performed to compare the mean values of the students' anticipated difficulties when they tackle a teamwork activity and significant mean differences were found, $F(4.12, 1204.06) = 15.48$, $p < 0.001$, $h^2 = 0.050$. Even though the average values of each variable are rather similar, post hoc comparisons found that scheduling and availability difficulties, and member involvement were the main concerns of students regarding teamwork, being the challenges in communication the students' least concerns (see Table 3).

In Table 3, the group of students who worked individually are compared to those who work in a team, regarding their teamwork anticipated difficulties. Simple effects analyses showed statistically significant mean differences in all the anticipated difficulties except for the lack of prior knowledge about team members, being the average values of the rest of the difficulties higher in the case of students who worked individually. From a practical point of view, the lack of knowledge among team

Table 3 Anticipated difficulties for students regarding teamwork

	Total		Team		Individual		Comparison		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	d
TEAM KNOWLEDGE	3.36	1.41	3.30	1.42	3.50	1.37	1.13	.26	0.14
AGENDA	3.80	1.24	3.69	1.27	4.04	1.16	2.29	.02	0.29
SOLO	3.56	1.35	3.43	1.39	3.86	1.20	2.51	.01	0.32
ADVANTAGE	3.52	1.39	3.41	1.44	3.78	1.22	2.10	.04	0.27
COMMUNICATION	3.13	1.35	2.99	1.37	3.44	1.26	2.70	<.01	0.34
PARTICIPATION	3.29	1.32	3.14	1.38	3.70	1.13	2.84	<.01	0.36
COMMITMENT	3.36	1.40	3.21	1.45	3.70	1.22	2.79	<.01	0.35
TOTAL	3.43	1.10	3.31	1.14	3.70	0.95	2.87	<.01	.36

TEAM KNOWLEDGE: Pre-existing lack of knowledge about team members; AGENDA: Agenda and availability difficulties; SOLO: Involvement of the members: "Some go their own way."; ADVANTAGE: Involvement of the members: "Some take advantage of the work of others."; REMOTE: Difficulties in remote communication; PARTICIPATION: Lack of participation in meetings; COMMITMENT: Lack of commitment

Table 4 Students' perceptions regarding the acquisition of skills

	Total		Team		Individual		Comparison		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	d
INTERPERSONAL	3.32	1.28	3.32	1.35	3.33	1.11	0.08	.94	0.01
CONFLICT	3.19	1.27	3.20	1.34	3.16	1.12	0.29	.77	0.04
NEGOTIATION	3.27	1.26	3.28	1.32	3.26	1.12	0.13	.90	0.02
ACTIVE	3.33	1.30	3.40	1.36	3.17	1.14	1.45	.15	0.18
COMMUNICATION	3.16	1.31	3.17	1.36	3.13	1.19	0.21	.84	0.03
THINKING	3.33	1.27	3.33	1.32	3.33	1.16	0.02	.98	<.01
ADAPTABILITY	3.31	1.30	3.35	1.35	3.22	1.19	0.80	.42	0.10
EMPLOYABILITY	3.37	1.25	3.54	1.25	2.98	1.16	3.65	<.01	0.46
TOTAL	3.30	1.14	3.34	1.21	3.20	0.97	0.99	.324	0.13

INTERPERSONAL: Generate/Develop interpersonal skills; CONFLICT: Facilitate conflict resolution; NEGOTIATION: Generate/Develop negotiation skills; ACTIVE: Foster active learning; COMMUNICATION: Improve oral communication; THINKING: Promote critical thinking; ADAPTABILITY: Improve adaptability; EMPLOYABILITY: foster employability-oriented skills

members do not seem to be a problem regardless the modality chosen ($d = 0.14$). Besides, the largest effect sizes were related to the challenges in remote communication ($d = 0.34$), and the lack of commitment ($d = 0.35$) and participation in meetings ($d = 0.36$) (see Table 3).

Finally, Table 4 collects the students' perceptions about the skills they acquire when they work collaboratively. According to the students' perceptions, all the skills investigated were similar and ranged from 3.16 to 3.37. However, RM-ANOVA found statistically significant mean differences ($F(4.12, 1204.06) = 2.77, p < 0.001, h^2 = 0.009$). Post hoc analyses found that according to students' perceptions, the average in interpersonal skills was statistically higher than conflict resolution skills and oral communication. The two-group mean comparison only found significant differences in the case of skills related to employability which were higher in the group of students who chose teamwork. It is interesting to note that only the potential of teamwork to foster employability-oriented skills showed a moderate effect size ($d = 0.48$).

4.2 Students' choice of the working modality in the assignment

Figure 1 displays the CHAID decision tree. The criterion variable was whether the student chose the teamwork or the individual option. All the variables that showed significant mean differences across the two groups were introduced in the analysis as predictors of the students' choice, along with the work-wise situation and obligations that limit their study time. The model classifies correctly 72.1% of the total of students in the sample. Besides, the correct classification of students who chose to work in teams and who preferred to work individually was 72.6% and 71.1% respectively.

Fig. 1 CHAID decision tree for the criterion variable: assignment modality chosen by the student (individual or teamwork). EDUCATION: Necessary for my education; PERFORMANCE: Improve your performance in the subject; AGENDA: Agenda and availability difficulties

In view of the decision tree, the best predictor of teamwork selection was the perceived need of the students for their education. According to the decision tree, it is more likely that students scoring more than three on this item will choose to work in a team. Among students who perceive teamwork as less crucial for their education, those aiming to enhance their performance were more likely to opt for group work. Conversely, within the subset of students not prioritizing performance improvement through teamwork, those with fewer scheduling constraints and greater availability were more prone to choose this modality. Thus, the decision tree diagram suggests that students who prefer individual work generally do not perceive collaborative tasks as essential for their education, do not prioritize performance enhancement through teamwork, and face limited scheduling availability.

4.3 Students’ perceptions of the aspects of teamwork requiring greater effort from them

During data collection, students working in teams were surveyed using a 5-point Likert-type scale to determine their preference for completing future assignments in teams or individually. Based on their responses, students were categorized into two groups: those scoring 4 or 5, indicating a preference for teamwork in future assignments ($n = 95$), and those scoring 1 or 2, indicating a preference for individual work ($n = 67$).

Significant mean differences were detected through a repeated measures analysis of variance (RM-ANOVA) comparing the mean values of students’ perceptions of teamwork contributions (see Table 5). The analysis yielded $F(4.85, 775.31) = 4.28, p < 0.001$, with an effect size of $\eta^2 = 0.026$. Post hoc pair-wise comparisons revealed no statistically significant differences except for leadership, which had the lowest average score among all aspects surveyed (see Table 5).

Regarding the comparison between students willing to work in teams for future papers and those preferring individual work, although average scores were higher

Table 5 Students’ perceptions regarding the aspects that have entailed greater effort during teamwork, disaggregated by students’ willingness to use teamwork for future assignments

	Total		Individually		Teamwork again		Comparison		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	d
MEETING	3.08	1.48	3.19	1.42	3.00	1.52	0.82	.41	0.13
LEADERSHIP	2.71	1.31	2.93	1.42	2.56	1.21	1.77	.08	0.28
DISTRIBUTION	3.14	1.35	3.48	1.33	2.89	1.14	2.76	<.01	0.44
FEEDBACK	3.02	1.43	3.22	1.43	2.88	1.41	1.50	.14	0.24
TRUST	2.94	1.43	3.24	1.44	2.73	1.40	2.28	.02	0.36
STEPS	3.10	1.32	3.21	1.37	3.02	1.28	0.90	.37	0.14
GOAL	3.01	1.39	3.18	1.38	2.89	1.40	1.28	.20	0.21
STYLE	3.15	1.39	3.30	1.45	3.05	1.35	1.11	.27	0.18
TOTAL	2.98	1.07	3.22	1.14	2.88	1.11	1.90	.06	0.30

MEETING: Kick-off of the first meeting; LEADERSHIP: Manage team leadership; DISTRIBUTION: Cooperation/Collaboration/Independent work; FEEDBACK: Feedback among teammates; TRUST: Trust and internal communication; STEPS: Accomplishment of intermediate steps; GOAL: Setting up a team common goal; STYLE: Homogenize the style and paper structure

among those favoring teamwork, only two aspects showed statistically significant differences with small effect sizes: workload distribution ($d = 0.44$) and internal communication and trust ($d = 0.36$).

4.4 Students’ perceptions of the extent to which teamwork helps in building learning communities in hybrid education

A repeated measures analysis of variance (RM-ANOVA) was conducted to compare the mean values of students’ perceptions regarding the contributions of teamwork (see Table 6). Significant mean differences were observed, $F(2.87, 460.56) = 2.88, p < 0.001$, with an effect size of $\eta^2 = 0.013$. Post hoc pair-wise comparisons indicated no statistically significant differences between the mean values of any pair of the four variables (see Table 6). However, when comparing students who would choose the teamwork modality for future papers with those who would prefer to work individually, statistically significant differences emerged between the two groups, with all effect sizes being large. According to students’ perceptions, the most substantial effect size was associated with the belief that teamwork facilitated assistance among peers and mutual benefit ($d = 2.46$).

4.5 Students’ intentions regarding the prospective modality for future assignments after having chosen teamwork this time

Figure 2 illustrates the CHAID decision tree regarding students’ decisions regarding teamwork or individual work on future papers. All variables demonstrating significant mean differences across the two groups were included as predictors of students’ choices. The model accurately classifies 91.4% of the total student sample. Furthermore, the correct classification rates for students intending to use teamwork in future papers and those preferring individual work were 83.6% and 93.8%, respectively.

The most significant predictor of students’ future engagement in teamwork was their valuation of the opportunity to assist peers and receive assistance from them (see Fig. 2). Students who value this aspect with a score exceeding three points are more likely to opt

Table 6 Students’ perceptions of the extent to which teamwork has contributed to building a learning community, disaggregated by students’ willingness to use teamwork for future assignments

	Total		Individually		Teamwork again		Comparison		
	M	SD	M	SD	M	SD	t	p	d
INTERACTION	3.32	1.34	2.15	1.12	4.15	0.96	-12.21	<.01	1.94
PARTICIPATION	3.26	1.37	2.01	1.07	4.15	0.96	-13.33	<.01	2.13
HELP	3.43	1.36	2.12	1.05	4.36	0.80	-15.40	<.01	2.46
CONNECTEDNESS	3.22	1.47	2.03	1.06	4.21	0.90	-14.13	<.01	2.25
TOTAL	3.33	1.27	4.22	0.70	2.07	0.90	-16.01	<.01	2.55

INTERACTION: Promoting and increasing interaction among peers; PARTICIPATION: Enhancing participation in the subject; HELP: Assisting peers and benefiting from the resulting feedback; CONNECTEDNESS: Decreasing student isolation in semi-presential teachings

Fig. 2 CHAID decision tree for the criterion variable: assignment modality chosen by the student (individual or in teams) for the next paper after having chosen to work in teams on the present paper. WORKLOAD: Decrease the workload; GRADES: Improve my grade in the subject; COMMUNITY: Create a learning community; HELP: Assisting peers and benefiting from the resulting feedback

for team-based modalities repeatedly. Moreover, this likelihood increases among students demonstrating an interest in establishing learning communities. Among students with intermediate interest in offering and receiving assistance, the decision to engage in team-based work is notably influenced by their pursuit of enhancing subject grades. Ultimately, students with low motivation to assist and be assisted have minimal probabilities of persisting in team-based modalities and tend towards individual work. However, within this latter group, the probability of opting for teamwork increases if students perceive that this choice would alleviate their workload.

5 Discussion and conclusions

Promoting student involvement to achieve more complete and lasting learning via "learning by doing" ultimately responds to constructivist postulates, which place the focus on the student and his or her relevant role in the generation of his or her own knowledge and learning. This student involvement is especially important in hybrid education environments where student motivation and self-regulation are key factors for the success of the educational experience.

The role that students' perceptions of the indispensability of teamwork for their educational pursuits have in the results is noteworthy. Interestingly, the effect sizes indicated that both instrumental, such as perception such as task efficiency, and intrinsic oriented perceptions, as students' perception of the necessity of teamwork for their education, are relevant from a practical point of view. Moreover, students who opted to work in a group believed that teamwork would enhance their efficiency, increase their engagement and performance, and foster a sense of responsibility. Ultimately, they perceived that working in a team would bolster their motivation more than those who chose to work individually. Additionally, it is observed that students who prefer individual work generally do not perceive collaborative tasks as essential for their education, do not prioritize performance enhancement through teamwork, and face limited scheduling availability.

These results align with what was observed by Volkov and Volkov (2015) when considering that there is a group of students who perceive the team as a means to advance their individual and collective knowledge (compared to another group that only aims to solve it effectively).

Those students who value that carrying out the teamwork is necessary for their education opt for this activity. Among them, those who think that teamwork allows them to develop interpersonal skills are more likely to opt for it. The improvement of communication skills and the drive to generate knowledge are some of the main perceived benefits of teamwork, but interpersonal benefits are also noted, such as acquainting with peers, helping them and receiving help, reducing isolation, and ultimately, promoting the creation of a learning community. This result is in line with Ruiz Ulloa et al. (2004) since students recognize that the teamwork's experience improves their interpersonal skills. In fact, the best predictor of returning to teamwork was the positive assessment of helping other colleagues and receiving help, as Pang et al. (2011) already pointed out. Among those students who do not consider the mutual help that facilitates teamwork to be especially important, other variables of a more practical nature, such as reducing workload or improving their grade, are also secondary predictors of the desire to repeat teamwork.

Employability also appears as an important factor for those who prefer teamwork with a moderate size effect, indicating the interest in equipping themselves with the necessary skills for the professional future. As Eitel (2018) points out, successful teamwork on university projects can contribute to the development of future professional skills in the workplace. Interestingly, the rest of the students' perceptions of acquisition of skills displayed low effect sizes and no significant mean differences were found when the two groups of students were compared.

On the negative side, practical aspects usually appear provoked by the distance or flexibility for the student of these types of teaching. The lowest perception about teamwork is effectiveness. Thus, scheduling and availability difficulties arise, along with challenges in remote communication, and the lack of commitment and participation in meetings. In fact, previous studies have shown that there is a relationship between satisfaction with teamwork and the time spent in class on that type of work (Oakley et al., 2007; Pfaff & Huddleston, 2003). However, in a hybrid environment, such as the one used for our research, it is much more complicated to dedicate time to teamwork in face-to-face sessions since many of the students cannot attend due to different incompatibilities. Moreover, the largest effect sizes in the students' perceived difficulties of teamwork when subjects who chose to work in groups were compared with those who completed the task individually are related to problems regarding in-group communication, participation, and commitment. Therefore, it can be posited that teammate trust is a relevant factor in explaining students' choice. Considering the outcomes of our study, it would be beneficial to implement preparatory measures prior to the commencement of teamwork. Such measures could facilitate enhanced interpersonal familiarity among students and foster confidence in their peers.

Additionally, the decision tree diagram suggests that students who prefer individual work generally do not perceive collaborative tasks as essential for their education, do not prioritize performance enhancement through teamwork, and face limited scheduling

availability. Coinciding with previous results in the literature, those who select individual work show greater distrust towards their colleagues, on the part of those who do it individually, confirming fear of free rider phenomena, as one of the most frequent drawbacks in line with previous research (Roberts & McInnerney, 2007; Chang, & Kang, 2016). In this sense, the results are aligned with Wolfe et al. (2016) who found as the first difficulty to encounter colleagues in the team who do not put enough effort. In fact, lack of communication and low individual responsibility were negative factors in teamwork experiences (Tseng & Yeh, 2013). Moreover, Ptaff and Huddleston (2003) find that the absence of people on the team who go “on their own” is one of the factors that predicts a positive attitude of students towards teamwork.

Our results suggest that perceptions related to the possible relationship between teamwork and the formation of learning communities (interaction, participation, mutual help, and connectivity) depend largely on students' satisfaction with teamwork. Indeed, it is those students who would do future teamwork display much higher levels of these perceptions. Furthermore, among students who show a high average level in the variable related to mutual help, the possibility of teamwork to create learning communities seems particularly important. These results are in line with Tseng and Yeh (2013) who showed how students who enjoyed working in groups had good relationships and trust with their team members. Likewise, this finding contributes evidence to that already detailed in the literature, indicating that, when the condition of student satisfaction is met, collaborative tasks contribute to the consolidation of learning communities (Slattery & Cleary, 2017).

5.1 Conclusions and future research

In summary, it is observed that those future educators who are more fully committed to their own learning and the development of their competencies tend to opt for teamwork. In contrast, future educators who focus on the potential drawbacks of teamwork, either because of difficulties in participating or distrust of their peers, tend to prefer individual work.

In this sense, we concur with the findings of Morgan-Thomas and Dudau (2019) in the context of online learning environments. In such settings, students tend to engage in activities that they perceive as most relevant or valuable for their learning. It is therefore essential to ensure that these activities are both useful and valuable (Naujokaitienė et al, 2020). It is evident that not all students, future teachers, are prone to teamwork a priori and therefore an effort of awareness and training to revert this effect is required. As Riebe et al. (2016) indicate, many educators may not have received any formal training in teaching methods or are not familiar with resources or collaborative approaches to develop students' teamwork skills. Moreover, as these same authors point out for some educators, it is not always clear how they should teach teamwork skills and it also implies an additional effort, namely transaction costs. It is clear that this awareness and training effort should be more intense with "future educators" who prefer individual work to avoid difficulties. This is especially important when it comes to technology integration into the classroom where the teacher's role becomes fundamental (Cabero-Almenara, Roig-Vila & Mengual-Andres, 2017). As Guri-Rosenblit (2018) indicates, the little attention paid to the crucial role of teachers

in online settings results in a restricted and moderate adaptation of the technologies in higher education worldwide.

Inadequate preparation can provoke or intensify negative perceptions of teamwork among students (Tombaugh & Mayfield, 2014). The future teacher must learn to establish a climate that encourages the active participation of students, the consensus of norms that facilitate the internal dynamics of the team and the definition of roles and schedules, as pointed out by Jaca et al. (2016). It is a path that he/she must travel from his/her own training. In addition, future educators must learn not to intervene excessively in the teams' internal dynamics when solving problems that may arise (Natoli, Jackling, & Seelanatha, 2014) and advance in cooperative learning dynamics (Liebech-Lien, 2021), not purely as from regular group work, but by working on social skills.

If effective teamwork is to be one of the objectives of the assignment, direct and detailed instructions are required on how to do it and how to solve the problems associated with such teamwork. These training instructions are required as part of the assignment itself. Teachers should introduce the concept of teamwork and how to best function in its implementation. Teachers can encourage future teachers to read about the topic, successful experiences and ideas that work, encouraging them to define teamwork to be carried out in the future. Initial team training sessions can be a good way to explain what is expected of participants, while also introducing elements of motivation. In addition, designing good teaching materials for collaborative learning is a demanding task for instructors, especially for teacher training. It requires offering the best conceptual materials while providing enjoyable team learning opportunities that can engage teams in working together for the entire duration of the class, as already indicated by Gomez et al. (2009). Future teachers should be taught to engage students through peer evaluation and to delve deeper into the process of evaluating and grading the work: process can be evaluated using a variety of measures, such as meeting minutes, peer and self-evaluations, students' email and chat exchanges, and progress reports. Definitively, teachers can help future teachers to develop the metacognitive skills they will need to succeed as future teachers of teamwork activities.

Certainly, further research is needed to build real communities of learning through teamwork, mitigating isolation, understanding which team assignments are more appropriate in these blended environments, and engaging the future educators to be trained to promote teamwork with their own future students. In particular, given that one of the aspects to improve in distance teaching is the reduction of students' feelings of isolation as Rasheed et al. (2020) suggest, continuing to work on how to use teamwork appropriately to reduce this feeling may be a promising line of future research.

In any case, we consider that the combination of teamwork with blended learning and perception of future educators intersects several interesting lines of research that, when connected, open interesting avenues for the future of education. Therefore, we consider that our humble findings can be an interesting contribution to continue exploring different strategies that help create robust learning communities in hybrid teaching, and

particularly in the training of future educators, an aspect that is perhaps the most original compared to other investigations.

Appendix. Survey items

Block I. Demographic and classification variables

1. Age
2. Gender (male, female, other/prefer not to answer)
3. Employment (Full-time, Part-time, Not employed)
4. Obligations limiting study time (Work, caregiving responsibilities, both, none)
5. I completed the paper (individual, team)

Block II. Impressions about teamwork from all students in the sample

Thinking about your experience while completing a team assignment, please answer the following questions:

6. In relation to teamwork, indicate to what extent it has been useful for you to:

Increase your motivation for the subject
 Improve your performance in the subject
 Take responsibility for your own learning
 Increase your involvement with the subject
 Collaborate to build useful and meaningful knowledge
 Develop your communication and knowledge transmission skills
 Perform the task more efficiently
 Improve my grade in the subject
 Decrease the workload
 Get to know my classmates
 Create a learning community
 Reduce the isolation of distance learning
 I consider teamwork tasks necessary for my education

7. To what extent do you consider that carrying out teamwork can be hindered by the following reasons:

Pre-existing lack of knowledge about team members
 Agenda and availability difficulties
 Involvement of the members: "Some go their own way."
 Involvement of the members: "Some take advantage of the work of others."
 Difficulties in remote communication.
 Lack of participation in meetings.

Lack of commitment.

8. Regarding the competencies and skills acquired through the completion of the task, assess to what extent it has allowed you to:

Generate/Develop interpersonal skills
 Facilitate conflict resolution
 Generate/Develop negotiation skills
 Foster active learning
 Improve oral communication
 Promote critical thinking
 Improve adaptability
 Foster employability-oriented skills.

Block III. Impressions about teamwork from individuals who chose to work in teams

9. What stages of the activity required the most effort and/or time?

Kick-off of the first meeting
 Leadership
 Cooperation/Collaboration/Independent work
 Constructive feedback among participants
 Trust and internal communication
 Completion of intermediate stages
 Unification towards a common goal
 Standardization of work styles and structures

10. To what extent do you consider that this proposed teamwork contributes to forming Learning Communities in the following aspects:

Promote and increase interaction with peers (classmates)
 Increase participation in the subject/course
 Assist peers and benefit from the resulting feedback
 Reduce student isolation in semi-presential teachings

11. How likely would you be to participate again in team activities? (1-5)

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Authors' contributions

JN designed the experiment, conducted theoretical and bibliographical analysis, prepared the survey, and drafted the initial article. DA performed the statistical analysis and contributed to the writing of the manuscript. AG directed

the project, coordinated the survey, and performed supervision and revision of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final manuscript.

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Data availability

Data will be openly available in open repositories, once the manuscript will be accepted.

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Authors accept journal's ethics guidelines and consent to participate. Authors avoid misrepresenting research results which could damage the trust in the journal, accepting ethics requirements in accordance to the journal submission guidelines.

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